

USING MACHINE LEARNING TO DETERMINE THE LEVEL OF INFECTION OF CERCOSPORA LEAF SPOT DISEASE IN COWPEAS

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ABSTRACT

Cercospora leaf spot disease is a fungal disease that affects cowpeas. Most cowpea farmers have a challenge of identifying the different levels of infection of the disease. In this paper, we carried out a study with an objective to help farmers identify the different stages of the cercospora leaf spot disease to stop the disease from spreading further. We used questionnaires to collect data and observed the properties of leaves of varying stages of infection. The data was analyzed using bar graphs and charts and the results show that farmers believe that this mobile application is going to help them to identify and differentiate the levels of infection. We used OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision Library), for image and video processing. Using color-blob detection, we were able to identify the cercospora leaf spot color code and the levels of infection of the leaves. Using the surface area covered, we computed to establish the percentage covered by the contours (spots of infected parts) which when compared to the whole surface area gives the level of infection. We tested the algorithm on 20 leaves and found 100% accuracy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cercospora leaf spot is a fungal disease that affects cowpea plants. It causes leaves to fall off and causes yield losses of up to 40% [1]. The disease is not seed transmitted but carried over to the next growing season on alternative hosts, as well as crop remains.

Cercospora leaf spots of cowpea begin as small, lighter colored areas which is almost yellow. Later they become bronze to dark grey, roughly circular to more elongated and up to 10 mm across [1]. The fungus produces masses of wind-borne spores on the lower surface of the leaf giving the spots a distinctive grey to dark powdery appearance. When held up to the light, the older leaf spots are darker, more reddish and often with a distinct ring. Dead areas fall out, giving a shot-hole appearance. The leaf withers as the spots join together which later dies and falls off.

The leaf spots vary in shape, size and color and could be confused with other similar symptoms. Therefore, better means of diagnosing the level of infection of the cercospora leafspot disease can be developed to help farmers prevent the spread of the disease to other plants.

Currently, there are no modern techniques for automatic detection and classification of the cercospora cowpea plant disease infection levels. This necessitates continuous monitoring of the

farm is required which requires more labor and expertise. In remote areas, farmers may have to go long distances to seek expert advices.

An automatic detection of plant disease is an important and cultural research domain as it may help in developing countries such as Uganda to improve production.

In this study, an android mobile application that cowpea farmers can use to tell cercospora disease is developed to help remove the drawbacks of traditional methods. The proposed application basically consists cercospora leaf spot disease recognition by using visually seen symptoms of disease, i.e. brown spots on the leaf. The application performs a video image frame processing on the infected leaf, diagnoses it and tells the level of infection. The treatment is suggested in English on the android mobile application.

2. RELATED WORK

Various methods have been proposed to diagnose diseases in plants. The method of measuring leaf disease severity using segmentation and histogram thresholding was suggested in [2]. Another method in [3] suggests color image feature extraction technique, this technique is known as color image segmentation. Using this technique it is easy to extract the various features of diseased leaf of cotton image. In [4] it describes the process of measuring sugarcane leaf area using pixel number statistics. Another approach described the process of calculating leaf area using CIELAB color space [5]. Authors have used a reference object to measure leaf area. Another process of detection and classification of leaves diseases applying K-means clustering, masking green-pixels and some other procedures and finally Configuring Neural Networks for Recognition. Authors of described the process of calculating leaf area. The activities of the authors was focused on to calculate leaf area. Some researchers have used image processing techniques for fast and accurate measurement of leaf area. Leaf area is measured using following steps: [6] image acquisition, image pre-processing, leaf region segmentation, region filling and area calculation. Some researchers use contour extraction technique for leaf region segmentation and others use threshold based segmentation [4]. In [5] methods that measured the affected leaf area through pixel number statistics were suggested.

Mobile applications have been developed with quite similar ideas. These applications have been implemented to identify pests and diseases of different crops. A case in point the PLANTIX which has a key feature of automated disease diagnosis. Farmers can upload a picture of the infected plant and the application will provide a diagnosis and steps to mitigate the disease. The application also provides the information on preventing the disease in the next cropping season. The application also features a library of diseases which farmers can refer to in case there is no connectivity [7].

CropDiagnosis is a mobile application aiming to improve pest management decisions by making crop diagnosis more accurate, selection of chemicals error-free and application assisted by personalised instructions. By evaluating the crop's details by type, location, soil, history and

threat's characteristics by type, appearance, progress as entered by the user through a smart questionnaire, the application suggests the most likely diagnosis [8].

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Algorithm

We used OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision Library) which is an open-source BSD-licensed library that includes several hundreds of computer vision algorithms. The document describes the OpenCV 2.x API, which is a C++ API. The OpenCV functionality we used was Image processing.

Image processing - an image processing module that includes linear and non-linear image filtering, geometrical image transformations (resize, affine and perspective warping, generic table-based remapping), color space conversion, histograms, and so on. [9]

Using OpenCV, blob detection is carried out through the computation of local extreme of some normalized derivatives of the linear scale-space image representation [10]. The blob detection provided complementary information about regions which cannot be obtained from edge detectors or corner detectors.

We used two image types for processing of the processing of images i.e.

Binary Images (Contains off or on values). This type of image will be used as a multiplier to mask regions within another image. [11]

Grayscale Images (Pixels range from least intense (black) to most intense (white))

Below are the steps we used for a blob extraction:

1. **Thresholding:** Convert the source images to several binary images by thresholding the source image with thresholds starting at minimum threshold (minThreshold). These thresholds are incremented by a threshold step (thresholdStep) until the maximum threshold (maxThreshold). So the first threshold is minThreshold, the second is (minThreshold + thresholdStep), the third is (minThreshold + 2(thresholdStep)), and so on following that sequence. [12]
2. **Grouping:** In each binary image, connected white pixels are grouped together. Let's call these binary blobs.
3. **Merging:** The centers of the binary blobs in the binary images are computed, and blobs located closer than the minimum distance between the blobs (minDistBetweenBlobs) are merged.
4. **Center & Radius Calculation:** The centers and radii of the new merged blobs are computed and returned.

After obtaining a blob, there are available methods of filtration which we apply to get closer to obtaining more accurate results in relation to analyzing the leaf. By color, this filter compares the intensity of a binary image at the center of a blob to the blob color. If they differ, the blob is filtered out. We use the blob color set to 0 to extract dark blobs and set the blob color to 255 to extract light blobs.

3.1.2. VIDEO IMAGE FRAME PROCESSING

This component consists of image enhancement, segmentation (blob detection), filtration scalar and area calculation.

In image enhancement, having received the video input from the camera, the application relays the video to the user via the camera-area on the application at a particular bit rate (Image Frame per second). Once the user taps the camera-area a selection of the image from each frame the video input is used as an independent image per second.

Under segmentation, the application goes through a range of colors fed to it to choose one color to convert each image of the video frame per second as the source image to binary imagery.

Under filtration, the application uses the color feature to determine the blob. We chose color over the other features of blob filtration such as Size, Shape and Brightness because color blob detection because it provides complementary information about regions which cannot be obtained from edge detectors or corner detectors.

Since cercospora cannot be identified by a single color such as red or brown, we have to use a range of colors associated with the infection. The key of infection ranges from yellow tending to dark brown. This means that we have to use scalar-vector classification to cater for all the possible colors.

We created a scalar that represents a 4-element vector. The type Scalar is widely used in OpenCV for passing pixel values. For example: For a color argument we can give, Scalar (a, b, c). We would be defining a BGR color such as: Blue = a, Green = b and Red = c. After using the color blob to detect the regions on the image which fall under the range selected, the application uses histogram data analysis to map contours on the camera-area. Contours are drawn by supplying specific parameters to the function (ClipLine) created to draw the lines on the camera-area. The parameters are the Rectangle of the camera-area (the coordinates of the image which form the vertices of the camera-area), and the coordinates of the two points between which to draw a line. The Clip-Line function is looped for the number of times until a contour is completely drawn.

Under Area calculation, we use the average surface area of all the contours of the infected regions on the leaf. We use the average to assume all the contours as one. During the development, we calibrated and found the area of the camera-area to be 150,000 mdpi². This is the rectangular block in which the video input is displayed to the user.

Since the Leaf is has no regular shape and cannot be rectangular to fill all the camera area, we have to calculate the surface area of the leaf by subtracting the lost area (as shown in the diagram below) from the entire area of the camera-area.

The lost area was obtained after multiple calibrations using known leaf areas (Leaves cut in regular shapes whose area was calculated) and subtracting it from the camera area.

Figure 1: Area calculation illustration.

The lost area was in the region of 5,000 mdpi² to 70,000 mdpi² in the first series of calibration using 10 leaves, this was later closed down to the region between 25,000 mdpi² and 45,000 mdpi² in the second series of calibration using 40 more leaves. As at the moment, the lost area is assumed as 25,000 mdpi².

$$\text{The infected area} = \frac{\text{Sum of Surface areas of contours}}{\text{Number of contours}} \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 1}$$

The infected area is the average surface area of all the contours.

Level Classifier, Using the surface area of the leaf and the surface area of the infected area, we use a scale of 1 to 5 to obtain a level of infection which is a double (caters for decimal values).

$$\text{Level} = \frac{\text{Surface Area of Infected Area} * 10}{\text{Total Leaf Area}} \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 2}$$

4. RESULTS

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

The video image frame input takes in the contours of the infected leaf using the camera provision on the mobile phone as seen in Fig 2. It then does diagnosis to return the results in image Fig 3. The results returned show the diagnosis result level of the infected leaf that is from level 1 to level 5, the date the diagnosis was carried out, the advisor comment and the prescription given to the farmer. The nearest pesticide shop within a 500m proximity to his location is also shown to the farmer using the google maps as seen in image Fig 4.

Table 1: Percentage of infection and corresponding measures

LEVEL OF INFECTION	% OF THE LEAF INFECTED	MEASURES TO BE TAKEN
Level 1	The leaf is clean	Maintain
Level 2	1-10%	Mild, Spray with Fungicides
Level 3	11-50%	Moderate, Spray with Fungicides.
Level 4	51-75%	Tending to severe, Uproot or Spray.
Level 5	76% and above	Severe, Uproot

5. FUTURE WORK

Improvement of the application with artificial intelligence that will enable the identification of the leaf edges. After this is done, a drone with a high resolution camera can be passed over the garden to analyze all the cowpea plants at once.

6. CONCLUSION

Image processing technique is very much essential to observe the intensity of disease. As the open eye observation may result poor accuracy and it may vary person to person. In this paper with the help of video image frame processing, the infected leaf has been scanned and analyzed. By counting the disease affected area and unaffected area, the percentage of disease affected area has been calculated. According to the percentage of disease affected area, the severity of disease can be understood; consequently appropriate measure can be taken to stop the spreading of the disease.

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